

On the Structure of Some Bis-Indole Alkaloids of a New Type : 11-(3'-Vobasiny)-Cleavamine : Structure of Capuvosidine

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The structures of several new bis-indole alkaloids have been unambiguously determined mostly by use of spectral methods and chemical correlations. These alkaloids are all constructed from a vobasine-type moiety linked to a cleavamine moiety.

AMONG numerous indole alkaloids of the Ibogaïne-type, represented either by catharanthine or by the antipodal coronaridine, none was known to have the cleavamine-type (i.e. seco-16,21 catharanthine or coronaridine) structure. However, this "missing link" is of importance as some therapeutically important bis-indole alkaloids like vinblastine and related compounds are formed by the linkage of two moieties: one of the velbanamine type, the other of the aspidospermane type (vindoline). At least for these complex indole alkaloids, it has been shown¹ that the tetracyclic seco-16,21 series (cleavamine) was derived from the pentacyclic (catharanthine) series through a fragmentation reaction. This has allowed the preparation of a number of compounds in this field of therapeutically useful compounds.

We have recently described¹ the isolation of capuvosine (1) from a rare Madagascar tree, *Capuronetta elegans* (Apocynaceae). This alkaloid represents the first example of a bis-indole alkaloid formed with a vobasine-type moiety linked to a cleavamine moiety. Tabernamine (5) later on isolated from *Tabernaemontana johnstonii* (Apocynaceae)² is an additional example of this new type of bis-indole alkaloid bearing no methoxyl group on the aromatic part of the ibogaïne moiety.

This structural peculiarity makes the determination of the linkage of the two moieties difficult. This junction was thought to be C₁₀, C_{3'} for capuvosine^{3,4}. It has been claimed however that tabernamine possesses a C₁₁, C_{3'} bond (Scheme 1). An unambiguous proof of this state of affairs was necessary.

TABLE—1

Capuronetta elegans *Pandaca boiteaut*

Capuvosine (1)	+	-
Dehydroxycapuvosine(2)	+	+
Capuvosine (3)	+	+
Dihydrocapuvosidine (4)	+	+

The accessibility of a new source of the same type of bisindole alkaloids isolated by us from a botanically related plant, *Pandaca boiteaut* (Table 1.) has allowed us to undertake a structural study on an entirely new basis.

It is known that the coupling reaction between vobasinal (6, Chart 1) and ibogaïne-type alkaloids, in acidic medium leads principally to compounds substituted on C-11 of the ibogaïne part (when there is a methoxyl group on C-10); conversely, if the methoxyl group lies on C-11, the substitution occurs at C-10. However, in the absence of any substituent on the aromatic part of the ibogaïne moiety, it is difficult to make any unambiguous prediction. Nevertheless, it is well-known^{5,7} that dihydroindoles have a greater nucleophilic reactivity on C-10.

We have now transformed capuvosidine (3), into a dihydroindole derivative (4). Careful analysis of its PMR spectrum has allowed us to define that the linkage was indeed between carbons 11 and 3' as shown in tabernamine².

Capuvosidine (3), amorphous, $[\alpha]_D^{20} - 7^\circ$ (c, 0.7%, CHCl₃), C₄₀H₄₈N₄O₂ (M⁺ 616) has a typical indole-indolenine UV chromophore: λ_{max}^{EtOH} (log ϵ): 228(4.61), 280(3.99), 286(3.99), 295(3.86); 230, 283, 295 and 340 in acidic medium. IR(CHCl₃): 1720(ester) and 1580 cm⁻¹ (indolenine). PMR spectrum (CDCl₃, δ_{ppm} , 240 MHz) shows an N-methyl group (2.55), methoxycarbonyl (2.45) and an ethylidene side-chain (1.75, 5.35) suggesting a vobasiny moiety. Only one indolic NH supports the presence of an indolenine grouping.

Capuvosidine is reduced by NaBH₄ in MeOH, as expected, to dihydrocapuvosidine (4) a minor alkaloid isolated from *Pandaca boiteaut* and an indole (resulting from a retro-Mannich reaction followed by reduction), dehydroxycapuvosine (2). Thus, all the alkaloids (1—4) isolated from *Capuronetta elegans* and *Pandaca boiteaut* are correlated.

Scheme 1

Therefore establishment of the linkage in dihydrocapuvosidine (4), would also settle the same in other bis-indole alkaloids of the same series. This has been possible by detailed PMR* spectral studies as discussed in the sequel.

Signals corresponding to the seven aromatic protons of compounds 1 and 4 are within 1 ppm bandwidth. A better resolution is obtained using d_6 -acetone and

allowing a study of solvent effects on some particular protons.

The aromatic protons of the vobasinyl part have been identified by comparison (Table 2) with vobasinol (6) and by decoupling experiments.

Assignment of the most downfield signal to H-9' is based on the spectral data of 5 or 6-methylindoles¹⁰.

(*) PMR. spectra have been recorded on the 240 MHz I.B.F. instrument⁹.

TABLE-2

PMR	Dihydrocapuvosidine <u>4</u>		Vobasinol (<u>6</u>)	
CDCl ₃				
240 MHz				
(δ ppm)				
H-9'	7.45 m		7.47 m	
H-12*	7.32 m		7.35 m	
H-10'				
H-11'	7.28 m		7.10 m	

(*) Solvent effect sensitive : Δ CDCl₃ - CD₂COCD₂ = -

The aromatic protons of the unsubstituted vobasinyl part being identified, the aromatic protons of the dihydroindole moiety could be easily assigned by difference and by decoupling experiments. Comparison of these data with those of the known dihydroindole alkaloids substituted at C-10, (Chart 1), clearly shows that dihydrocapuvosidine (4) is substituted at C-11.

Chart 1

Schematic Representation of the Aromatic Protons of the "DIMERS" Substituted on the Aromatic Ring

I. Dihydroindoles substituted at C-10 :

 a) 10-(16-eburnamyl) Pleiocarpinine^a

 b) 10-(3'-dregaminyl)-venalstonine⁷

 II. 11-3'-vobasinyl-aspidospermidine : (dihydrocapuvosidine, 4)

The configuration at C-3' now remains to be defined. The same configuration at this centre in vobamine (11-(3'-vobasinyl) vobamine) has not been

rigorously established⁸ though the nucleophilic attack of the vobamine moiety on vobasinol, during hemisynthesis, is expected to occur at the less hindered site (3 α) of the vobasinol. The chemical shifts of the C-3' β protons of vobamine and 16-epivobamine confirm this hypothesis.

In the case of capuvosidine (3) and related dimeric compounds the C-3' proton appears at about 4.50 ppm, i.e. at higher field than its analogue in the vobamine series (5.29 ppm) and with a chemical shift similar to that observed for 16'-epivobamine (4.7 ppm) where there is a shielding by the carbomethoxy group. It was only the observation of the shifting of the C-3' proton resonance for 16'-epi derivatives in our dimer series that allowed us to determine that we were dealing with an analogue of the vobamine series. Thus, when the epimerization was carried out on 2 the C-3' proton signal was seen to undergo a shift (4.55 $\rightarrow$ 4.12) allowing the conclusion that the configuration at C-3' for capuvosidine and related compounds is probably 3 β -H as in vobamine.

The above observation led us to revise our originally proposed structure of capuvosine to 1, the vobasinyl moiety being linked through its C-3' with the C-11 of the ibogaine part. This study also indicates that in acidic conditions (MeOH/HCl) an indole without any substituent on the aromatic ring has greater nucleophilicity at position C-11.

Experimental

Capuvosidine (3) : Amorphous, [α]_D²⁰ -7° (c : 0.7 ; CHCl₃), C₄₀H₄₂N₄O₉ (high resolution mass spectrometry). UV : λ_{max}^{EtOH} (log ϵ) : neutral 228 (4.61), 280 (3.99), 286 (3.99), 295 (3.86) nm ; acid : 230, 283, 295, 340 nm. IR : 3430 (NH), 1720 (ester). PMR (60 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS $\delta=0$) : 1.0 t, 3H, C-18 H ; 1.75, d (J=7 Hz), 1H, C-18 H ; 2.45, s, 3H, CO₂CH₃ ; 2.55, s, 3H, NCH₃ ; 6.7-7.6, 7H (aromatic) ; 8.0 1H, NH (indolic). MS (rel. intensity) : 616 (M⁺, 35), 436 (41), 423 (72), 182 (51), 181 (100), 180 (61), 138 (15), 124 (18), 122 (82).

Reduction of Capuvosidine (3) by NaBH₄ to 2 and 4 : The reduction of capuvosidine (3) by sodium borohydride, in methanolic solution, leads to a mixture of the derivatives 4 (70%) and 2 (30%). If the reduction is carried out in alkaline medium (NaOH), 2 becomes the major product :

Dehydroxycapuvosine (2) : Amorphous, [α]_D²⁰ -98° (c, 1% ; CHCl₃), C₄₀H₄₀N₄O₈ (high resolution mass spectrometry). UV : λ_{max}^{EtOH} (log ϵ), 232 (4.63), 288 (4.15), 295 (4.11) nm. IR : 3460 (NH), 1720 (ester). PMR : (60 MHz, CDCl₃, TMS $\delta=0$) : 0.87, t, 3H, C-18 H ; 1.67, d (J=7 Hz), 3H, C-18' H ; 2.44, s, 3H, CO₂CH₃ ; 2.57, s, 3H, NCH₃ ; 4.55, m, 1H, C-3' H ; 5.30, q (J=J'=7Hz), 1H C-19' H ; 6.7-7.4, m, 7 aromatic protons ; 7.55, m, 2H, NH indolic. MS (rel. intensity) : 618 (M⁺, 38), 438 (28), 182 (65), 181 (98), 180 (83), 138 (100), 124 (24), 122 (96).

Dihydrocapuvosidine (4): Amorphous, $C_{40}H_{50}N_4O_2$ (high resolution mass spectrometry. Ms (rel. intensity): 618 (M⁺, 98), 586 (59), 436 (98), 423 (96), 194 (73), 190 (100), 183 (85), 182 (100), 181 (98), 180 (100), 138 (81), 124 (100), 122 (100).

16-epi-Dehydroxycapuvosine: Dehydroxycapuvosine **2** (225 mg) was dissolved in 20 ml of anhydrous methanol in which 200 mg of sodium have been previously dissolved. The mixture was refluxed under nitrogen atmosphere for 24 hr. After extraction, a mixture of starting material, 16-epi-dehydroxycapuvosine and a third unknown minor product was obtained.

16-epi-Dehydroxycapuvosine (27%), separated by preparative TLC, is amorphous. There is no difference observed in the MS, IR or UV in comparison with dehydroxycapuvosine.

The following signals are displayed in the PMR spectrum: 2.48, s, 3H, NCH₃; 3.45, s, 3H, CO₂CH₃; 4.12, s, 1H, C-3' H.

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